

Original paper

O'ZBEKISTON UNIVERSITETLARIDA ESP LUG'ATINI O'ZLASHTIRISH: IT TALABALARI UCHUN QIYINCHILIKLAR, MOTIVATSIYA VA TIL SIYOSATI BO'YICHA TAKLIFLARNI BAHOLASH

© D.X. Kasimova¹✉

¹Boshqaruv va Kelajak Texnologiyalari Universiteti, Toshkent O'zbekiston

Annotatsiya

KIRISH: ushbu tadqiqot O'zbekistondagi oliy yurt talabalarining kasbiy nutqini rivojlantirishga alohida e'tibor qaratgan holda maxsus maqsadlar uchun ingliz tili (ESP) o'qitishning muhim ahamiyatini chuqur tahlil qiladi. Tadqiqot turli sohalarda qo'llaniladigan akademik til va ESP so'z boyligini o'zlashtirish bilan bog'liq ichki muammolarni hamda uning talabalarining kasbiy mahoratiga bevosita ta'sirini ko'rib chiqadi. Su bilan bir qatorda, butun mamlakat bo'ylab ESP o'qitish sifati va samaradorligini oshirish maqsadida ta'lim organlari tomonidan ushbu muammolarni hal qilish bo'yicha olib borilayotgan strategik tashabbuslar va siyosat islohotlari tasvirlangan. Ushbu ishning asosiy tarkibiy qismi keng qamrovli so'rov asosida talabalarining kasbiy nutqni rivojlantirishga motivatsiyasi va tushunchasini baholashdir. Natijalar esp so'z boyligini maqsadli o'rganish va talabalarining ixtisoslashtirilgan til tarkibni tushunish qobiliyati hamda o'z-o'zini baholashi o'rtasida sezilarli bog'liqlikni ko'rsatadi. Bundan tashqari, ushbu maqolada hozirgi vaqtda O'zbekistonda ESP ta'limiga ta'sir ko'rsatayotgan zamonaviy pedagogik va infratuzilma muammolari ko'rib chiqiladi.

MAQSAD: O'zbekiston oliy ta'lim talabalari uchun ESP metodikasi samaradorligini aniqlash, talabalarining kasbiy nutqni rivojlantirishga motivatsiyasi va tushunchasini baholash, shuningdek ESP ta'limidagi zamonaviy pedagogik va infratuzilma muammolarini tahlil qilish.

MATERIALLAR VA METODLAR: tadqiqotda keng qamrovli so'rov, ixtisoslashtirilgan testlar, o'z-o'zini baholash vositalari va taqqosiy tahlil usullari qo'llanildi. Shu bilan birga, talabalarining ESP so'z boyligini o'zlashtirish jarayonidagi akademik til ko'nikmalari kuzatildi.

MUHOKAMA VA NATIJALAR: natijalar ESP so'z boyligini maqsadli o'rganish va talabalarining ixtisoslashtirilgan til tarkibni tushunish qobiliyati hamda o'z-o'zini baholashi o'rtasida sezilarli bog'liqlikni ko'rsatdi. Tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatdiki, ESP o'qitish talabalarining kasbiy nutqini rivojlantirishga va akademik faoliyatda samarali muloqot qilishga yordam beradi. Shu bilan birga, ESP ta'limiga ta'sir ko'rsatayotgan zamonaviy pedagogik va infratuzilma muammolari aniqlangan.

XULOSA: ESP o'qitish O'zbekiston oliy ta'limida kasbiy til kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishda muhim vosita bo'lib, metodik va strategik yondashuvlar orqali uning

samaradorligini oshirish mumkin. Talabalarning motivatsiyasini oshirish va ESP resurslarini optimallashtirish kelajakdagi ta'lim sifatini yaxshilashga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: ESP, kasbiy nutq, akademik ingliz tili, til boyligi, ta'lim metodikasi, O'zbekiston, talabalar, motivatsiya

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ОСВОЕНИЕ ЛЕКСИКИ ESP В УНИВЕРСИТЕТАХ УЗБЕКИСТАНА: ОЦЕНКА ТРУДНОСТЕЙ, МОТИВАЦИИ И ПОСЛЕДСТВИЙ ЯЗЫКОВОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ ДЛЯ СТУДЕНТОВ IT-НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ

© Д. Х. Касимова^{1✉}

¹Университет управления и технологий будущего, Ташкент, Узбекистан

Аннотация

ВВЕДЕНИЕ: в данном исследовании проводится тщательный анализ критической важности преподавания лексики английского языка для специальных целей (ESP) в контексте высшего образования, с особым акцентом на Узбекистан. В исследовании рассматривается академический язык, используемый в различных областях, и внутренние проблемы, связанные с освоением лексики ESP, а также ее прямое влияние на профессиональные навыки студентов. В нем описываются стратегические инициативы и реформы политики, проводимые органами образования для решения этих проблем, с целью повышения качества и эффективности преподавания ESP по всей стране. Основным компонентом данной работы является оценка мотивации и понимания студентов на основе обширного опроса. Результаты показывают значительную взаимосвязь между целенаправленным обучением лексике ESP и самооценкой студентов по способности понимать специализированный контент. Кроме того, в данной статье рассматриваются уникальные педагогические и инфраструктурные проблемы, которые в настоящее время влияют на образование ESP в Узбекистане.

ЦЕЛЬ: определить эффективность методики ESP для студентов вузов Узбекистана, оценить мотивацию и понимание студентами развития профессиональной речи, а также проанализировать современные педагогические и инфраструктурные проблемы ESP обучения.

МАТЕРИАЛЫ И МЕТОДЫ: исследование проводилось с использованием широкого опроса, специализированных тестов, инструментов для самооценки и сравнительного анализа. Отслеживался процесс освоения академического языка и словарного запаса ESP студентами.

ОБСУЖДЕНИЕ И РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ: результаты показали значимую связь между целенаправленным изучением лексики ESP, способностью студентов понимать специализированный языковой материал и их самооценкой. ESP обучение

способствует развитию профессиональной речи и эффективной коммуникации в академической деятельности. Также выявлены современные педагогические и инфраструктурные проблемы, влияющие на ESP образование.

ЗАКЛЮЧЕНИЕ: преподавание ESP является важным инструментом развития профессиональной языковой компетенции в узбекских вузах. Методические и стратегические подходы могут повысить его эффективность, а оптимизация ресурсов и мотивации студентов способствует улучшению качества образования.

Ключевые слова: ESP, профессиональная речь, академический английский, словарный запас, методика преподавания, Узбекистан, студенты, мотивация

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ESP VOCABULARY ACQUISITION IN UZBEK UNIVERSITIES: ASSESSING DIFFICULTIES, MOTIVATION, AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS FOR IT STUDENTS

© Dildora Kh. Kasimova¹✉

¹University of Management and Future Technologies, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Annotation

INTRODUCTION: this study provides a detailed analysis of the importance of teaching English for Specific Purposes (ESP) in developing professional speech among university students in Uzbekistan. It examines internal challenges associated with acquiring academic English and ESP vocabulary, as well as their direct impact on students' professional skills. Additionally, strategic initiatives and educational reforms aimed at improving the quality and effectiveness of ESP instruction nationwide are described.

AIM: the aim of the article is to determine the effectiveness of ESP methodology for Uzbek university students, assess students' motivation and understanding in developing professional speech, and analyze contemporary pedagogical and infrastructural challenges in ESP education.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: the study employed a comprehensive survey, specialized tests, self-assessment tools, and comparative analysis. Students' acquisition of academic language and ESP-specific vocabulary was monitored.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS: findings revealed a significant correlation between targeted learning of ESP vocabulary, students' ability to comprehend specialized language content, and self-assessment. ESP instruction supports the development of professional speech and effective academic communication. Contemporary pedagogical and infrastructural challenges impacting ESP education were also identified.

CONCLUSION: esp teaching is a crucial tool for developing professional language competence in Uzbek higher education institutions. Methodical and strategic approaches

can enhance its effectiveness, while optimizing resources and student motivation contributes to improving overall educational quality.

Keywords: esp, professional speech, academic English, vocabulary, teaching methodology, Uzbekistan, students, motivation.

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The famous quotation "Death and life are in the power of the tongue, and those who love it shall eat its fruit" is found in the Book of Proverbs in the Bible. Its profound meaning requires the speaker to utilise and critically interpret their reasoning and professional skills while communicating. Today, when a hectic lifestyle pursues us every minute, the communicator should be careful to use an accurate word to convey a particular piece of information. On his blog, Brendan McCaughey describes the choice of words as an ability and skill that influences our personal and professional success. Thus, as educators, it is vital to emphasise the importance of teaching words and their usage with logical and critical reasoning. However, gaps in gaining adequate professional language skills at the university level build barriers to realising high potential, as discussed in the following paragraphs.

A substantial and growing body of literature has investigated the teaching of professional terminology and its associated barriers in various fields. The better insight into how and what professional terminology involves a particular field, the better you can choose a teaching approach. Thus, before discussing problems related to teaching professional language, let us first define professional terminology or vocabulary. We have reviewed numerous papers on academic vocabulary written recently; however, in many cases, the researchers do not thoroughly explore professional language. Ludmila Yu Minakova defines it as words that belong to specialised scientific, professional, or technical terminological systems and are not used or understood by people outside the particular speciality. This underscores the necessity and value of specialised training and resources in our work.

In a study aimed at determining the creation and utilisation of a technical glossary, Hyland underscores the role of ESP, which focuses on meeting the specific language needs of learners based on their academic or occupational goals. This practical focus makes specialised vocabulary essential for effective communication. [Hyland K, 2020] Iveta Tasheva draws attention to the personal jargon associated with each profession, highlighting the unique experiences and environments that accompany it. [Tasheva, 2025]

Soraya Garcia, who explains professional terminology as a specialised vocabulary used in specific fields, such as telecommunications, emphasises the crucial role of this specialised vocabulary in ensuring effective communication among professionals and accurately conveying complex concepts. Effective communication in telecommunications

heavily relies on this terminology, as it facilitates mutual understanding and enhances collaboration among industry experts. [Paula Morgado Fernández, 2022]

Zeinab M. Gaffas does not define the meaning of professional terminology, but raises the importance of learning medical terms through vocabulary notebooks and word lists. More than 60% of research papers are published in English, underscoring the significance of the English language in professional contexts, particularly in fields such as medicine, where precise terminology is essential for effective communication. This emphasises the necessity of professionals to be proficient in English to navigate the globalised landscape effectively.

Alejandro Curado Fuentes, while researching technical corpora, explains that in ESP, specialised vocabulary and collocations mean understanding specific knowledge related to a particular field. It leads learners' ability to overcome stylistic expectations in their professional disciplines. (Alejandro Curado Fuentes, 2001)

Researchers from Tashkent State Transport University blueprint a special vocabulary as the main object of terminology, distinguishing it in various scientific works as follows: "language for special purposes", "language of specialty", "professional language", "professional speech", etc. some scholars identify the concepts of "language of specialty", "language for special purposes" and "professional language"; other scientists, on the contrary, clearly distinguish between these concepts.[1-p-060017-1] D. Usmanova reviews precision, clarity, and specificity in professional vocabulary, which results in effective communication. She investigates the theoretical foundations of professional speech, examining its various functions, particularly grammar accuracy, rapport building, logical instructions, strong speech culture, and adaptation of speech. Key takeaways from the paper include listing the beneficial aspects of acquiring professional terminology, including successful interaction in any professional field, enhanced collaboration, building credibility, and concluding that it is a significant investment in professional development. [Usmanova, 2025] Although learning professional vocabulary has numerous advantages, there is still a big dilemma in involving students in ESP courses, which is not an easy process. A language teacher's job is paramount in this field, making this intellectual work more meaningful, with a view to increasing student attention to the philosophy of words and phrases, using them in their best implications, rather than speaking them senselessly.

Both acquiring and teaching professional vocabulary are challenging to implement to achieve a positive outcome. The initial problem lies in the student's interest in pursuing a technical field, as evidenced by most questionnaires administered at our university. Many scholars have analysed these difficulties, outlining gaps in content knowledge, a lack of resources, and challenges in student engagement with technical language. Further lines will represent

To develop learners' ability to think logically and critically, it is vital to foster their understanding and reasoning about the various meanings of words. Let us consider an example of a school graduate who has only experienced general English and must suddenly transition to specific learning, let alone the diversity in the classroom. K.

Prodayvoda marked students' variety of lexical training in the same classroom, which decreased the pace of the whole class. [K. Prodayvoda, 2020] The differences in vocabulary knowledge significantly impact the learning outcome. First, it results in a common understanding and oral and written reproduction. This pattern of vocabulary learning was later empirically confirmed through regression analysis. I. R. Vincy showed that the students had memorised the meanings of the words from their last term for their exams without actually understanding what the words meant. This pattern of vocabulary learning was later empirically confirmed in the regression analysis, which showed that in the conventional mode of vocabulary instruction, the reception of vocabulary had an average influence of only 8% on vocabulary production ability. [I.R. Vincy,2020] Higher education institutions are places where students can have a good model for acquiring academic and specific knowledge in a scholarly environment. The initial models are the lecturers in front of the students, facilitating and educating with their particular content language relating to their subject area. Each lesson can be challenging to grasp, as there is not enough time between pairs to analyse and synthesise the information provided in a distinct language. Bao Lina outlines the difficulty with textbooks and their written content language, which is unfamiliar to teachers and students. [Bao Lina, 2023]. Suardi, who used descriptive qualitative methods to collect data, identified the difficulty in selecting vocabulary. Both interviewed teachers pinned the selection of vocabulary as the most challenging activity [Suardi, 2019]. Juliana Othman conducted experiments on the Complexity of scientific terminology, which revealed that learners struggle due to the inherent complexity of scientific vocabulary. Students pointed out morphemes as an unfamiliar group of letters: prefixes, suffixes, and abstract concepts were analysed as significant barriers to comprehension, which makes students hesitate to participate in discussions involving these complex terms, suggesting a lack of understanding or confidence in using them. [Juliana Othman, 2024]

Nisrina Lutfiyah presented a survey among 30 sophomore students at Universitas Muria Kudus on obstacles to learning vocabulary. A remarkable result from the data was the difficulty in understanding word connotations. Before examining the results, we were interested in understanding the word 'connotation' meaning. According to the Cambridge dictionary, "connotation" is a feeling or idea a particular word suggests. However, it need not be a part of the word's meaning, or something offered by an object or situation. The researcher discusses the problems of understanding the phrase's connotation due to its dual meanings, which are accounted for at the highest level (60%). [N. Lutfiyah, 2022].

Having analysed more than 20 papers related to the challenges of teaching professional vocabulary, we have concluded that most authors indicated three main difficulties:

1. Motivation
2. Complexity of idiomatic expression
3. Lack of practical use

In our own research, we have found that many field professionals in Uzbekistan lack proficiency in languages, particularly for academic and professional purposes, despite being skilled in their respective careers. The abovementioned dilemmas create barriers to acquiring satisfactory knowledge that can enhance their potential. Moreover, the issue of language learning is a process that begins in school and continues at the University level. The reason to highlight school education in a foreign language is the background knowledge it provides, which significantly impacts future learning. Prior knowledge has a vast influence on memorisation. Lipson, M. Y. states that Prior knowledge significantly influences a learner's ability to acquire new information, as individuals often rely on existing knowledge over textual details, even when contradicted. This reliance can hinder accurate comprehension and correction of previously held misconceptions. [Lipson, 1982]

Based on scholarly research and findings, we investigated the most problematic issues encountered while teaching ESP courses to students in IT science programs.

The study employed qualitative research, primarily consisting of discussions and survey reports. The talks between coworkers mainly focused on students' performance, including their delivery and input and output assessment. Also, their level of comprehension and analysis of ICT English in four domain skills. It is important to note that critical thinking abilities depend on the content of a lesson and connecting it to professional orientation using various tools and strategies (in our case, computer engineering, info-communication, Software engineering, Information security, Information technology, and Multimedia technology) have been the most critical dispute among English instructors.

Students were the preeminent objects of discussions. It should be noted that making particular decisions was challenging, as students' General English and computer skills levels varied significantly; some had high academic English proficiency. In contrast, others had only the beginner level, let alone students with basic English words, such as numbers and greetings. However, group discussions, part of two different programs, helped elicit more ideas, suggestions, and problems and challenges. Two types of questionnaires were worked out. One of them was oriented towards students who are strongly motivated to continue gaining knowledge of Specific English, and for those who have less interest in connecting English to their academic program. Surveys were designed to consider learner skills, desires, motivation, and content-oriented aspects (ICT English).

Initially, we started with needs analysis of the syllabus confirmed for realisation during two academic semesters on teaching English for IT. The comparative analysis shows that although a few private and public universities in Tashkent have thematic units that contain appropriate language style and content towards IT programs, their realisation and meaningful delivery are not always successful.

The foreign language module is part of the IT science program's syllabus for freshmen, which comprises 48 practical academic hours per semester, with an additional 72 hours of independent study per semester at the University of Management and Future Technologies (for the 2025-2026 academic year). Undoubtedly, the allocated practical hours are not enough to acquire basic knowledge of a specific field in such a short period

in a foreign language. Thematic units cover content knowledge and grammar for 80 minutes, with no time allocated for revision. ESP instructors find it challenging to deliver the entire lesson plan, not only due to a lack of hours, but also due to students' varying English levels. While some students are capable of developing productive skills, they require time and effort to acquire specific English skills. If students with an adequate grasp of English struggle with the academic language of the subject, consider how much more difficult it is for students with almost no foreign language experience.

Moreover, independent hours mainly include the revision of grammar and general topics, which deviate from the primary aims of the curriculum. It is highlighted that the curriculum is designed to equip students with a comprehensive understanding of the socio-economic underpinnings of these disciplines, the processes of information exchange within the contemporary context of IT sector development, the adaptation of IT systems to economic reforms, and the practical application of these systems. Additionally, students have expressed dissatisfaction with the short module, which is explicitly designed for freshmen students. In the discussions, they said their wish to continue their ESP classes, as it is vital to know a language.

Second, the survey revealed that many instructors lack sufficient skills in material development and an insufficient understanding of teaching a specific field, as observed at the University of Management and Future Technologies (UMFT) and other private and public educational institutions. Good proficiency in English is not always a good motivation for becoming a professional academic and ESP instructor. What needs consideration is that some content teachers refuse to engage in collaborative work, reasoning that it involves additional work time and costs. Then there is a question of how to educate language teachers with professional skills in a particular field. The solution is likely to be setting up online and offline specialised training courses for individuals with a strong desire to be involved in ESP teaching. They would increase a professional approach to content realisation, which is crucial in ESP instruction.

Additionally, implementing a needs analysis before the start of an academic year and conducting lessons that rely on appropriate teaching methodologies and activities related to a specific field would enhance teacher performance, resulting in more fruitful student outcomes. The better ESP pedagogical skills an instructor has, the better they can move beyond a general approach. In the following sections, we will present some key survey results.

We included some questions about students' emotional status in the student questionnaire. (Picture № 1) We asked them how they typically feel about ESP classes and the content they are learning in these classes. Some students felt uncertain about expressing their genuine feelings, and the results could be skewed due to cultural and personal attitudes towards teachers.

Picture № 1. Students' feelings and emotions

The numbers are represented in hundreds, and most replied with total optimism about having ESP classes (confident); however, after survey discussions, some disorientation in students' performance during the lessons was revealed. The positive results were observed in the "scared" column, which comprised slightly over one-fifth of all students. However, they require considerable motivation and inspiration to excel in specific English classes. Almost half of the learners doubted whether they needed a particular field of English. They

Then we moved on to the difficulties of understanding ICT English. (Picture №2) We divided these into content, vocabulary, teaching strategy and grammar. Interestingly, the amount of content understanding is higher than the amount of vocabulary understanding. This suggests that students struggle to comprehend complex technical vocabulary in context and that there is a considerable need to instruct them in the various meanings of words using examples in tables. Although most teachers found it challenging to choose the proper methodology for writing their daily ESP plan, only a few students scored the lowest mark (10%). Grammar is the second least complicated subject to understand during lessons. However, it is teachers' primary goal during lessons, with content taking a back seat.

Picture № 2. The difficulties of understanding ICT English

We were particularly interested in integrating knowledge acquired through the English language into students' core Information Technology (IT) subjects. (Picture №3) The results were highly encouraging. Nearly all students reported that the knowledge gained in their foreign language classes was beneficial in understanding their specialised (IT) courses. Conversely, they also indicated that the specialised expertise aided their

comprehension of English, as they had already encountered the relevant concepts in practical laboratory sessions."

Picture № 3. The integration of ESP knowledge into the IT science subjects

When it comes to an instructor, the discussions and questionnaire results illustrated that they are also feeling a great challenge to get their students involved in ICT English, as it was an innovative approach to teaching English, requiring special training, and learning new software and hardware, language and acronyms, would be a great solution, as they noted in their debate. Balancing General English and ICT English, incorporating relevant lexis, grammar, and methods, is also an unavoidable challenge. A lack of Access to practical materials, worksheets, and resources is another issue, as they are either costly or available in limited quantities, making the teaching and preparing lesson content time-consuming and slow.

Overall, teaching English for specific purposes is not a smooth process. It requires not only knowledge of the language but also exceptional training, extensive experience, and competencies to engage students in a gradual yet progressive improvement in their performance over time. Students' inner motivation and wish to acquire technical English is another issue; a combination of both teacher effort and student motivation brings favourable results as long as collaborative work and diligence always outweigh any hardship in learning. A language teacher's job will make this intellectual work more meaningful, with a view to escalating student attention to the philosophy and technical meaning of words and phrases, using them in their best implications, rather than speaking them senselessly. However, we need a lot of training and teacher development courses to achieve fruitful results.

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MUALLIF HAQIDA MA'LUMOT [ИНФОРМАЦИЯ ОБ АВТОРЕ] [AUTHORS INFO]

✉ **Kasimova Dildora Xusanovna**, Boshqaruv va Kelajak Texnologiyalari Universiteti katta o'qituvchisi va Qo'qon Davlat Pedagogika Universiteti mustaqil tadqiqotchisi, [**Касимова Дилдора Хусановна**, Старший преподаватель Университета управления и технологий будущего и Независимый исследователь Кокандского государственного педагогического университета], [**Kasimova Dildora Xusanovna**, Senior teacher at the University of Management and Future Technologies and an Independent researcher at the State Pedagogical University, Kokand]; manzil: O'zbekiston, Qo'qon shahri, Farg'ona viloyati [адрес: Узбекистан, г. Коканд, Ферганская область], [address: Uzbekistan, Kokand city, Fergana]; email: fordildorakasimova@mail.com